

where $D_\beta, -L_\beta, -U_\beta$ are the diagonal, strictly lower and strictly upper triangular matrices obtained from A_β and D_1 is an auxiliary nonnegative diagonal matrix, L_1 is an auxiliary strictly lower triangular matrix and $0 \leq L_1 \leq L_\beta$.

If we choose certain auxiliary matrices, we can get the classical iterative methods.

1. The PSOR method

$$D_1 = \frac{1}{r}(1-r)D, L_1 = 0$$

$$\tilde{L}_r = (D_\beta - rL_\beta)^{-1}[(1-r)D_\beta + rU_\beta] \quad (6)$$

2. The PAOR method

$$D_1 = \frac{1}{r}(1-r)D, L_1 = 0$$

$$\tilde{L}_{rw} = (D_\beta - rL_\beta)^{-1}[(1-w)D_\beta + (w-r)L_\beta + wU_\beta] \quad (7)$$

We need the following definitions and results.

Definition 2.1 ([3]). A matrix A is a Z-matrix if $a_{ij} \leq 0$, for all $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n, i \neq j$.

Definition 2.2 ([3]). A matrix A is an M-matrix if A is a nonsingular Z-matrix, and $A^{-1} \geq 0$.

Definition 2.3 ([7]). Let $M, N \in R^{n \times n}$, the splitting of $A = M - N$ is called a regular splitting if $M^{-1} \geq 0$ and $N \geq 0$.

Lemma 2.1 ([3]). Assume that $A = M - N$ is a regular splitting of A . The splitting is convergent if and only if $A^{-1} \geq 0$.

Lemma 2.2 ([3]). Assume that A is an irreducible nonnegative matrix, then

(1) A has a positive real eigenvalue equals to its spectral radius;

(2) To $\rho(A)$, there corresponds an eigenvector $x > 0$;

(3) $\rho(A)$ is a simple eigenvalue of A .

Lemma 2.3 ([4]). Assume that A is a nonnegative matrix, then

(1) If $\alpha x \leq Ax$ for some nonnegative vector $x, x \neq 0$, then $\alpha \leq \rho(A)$;

(2) If $Ax \leq \beta x$ for some positive vector x , then $\rho(A) \leq \beta$. Moreover, if A is irreducible and there is a positive vector x such that $0 \neq \alpha x \leq Ax \leq \beta x$, then

$$\alpha \leq \rho(A) \leq \beta.$$

Lemma 2.4 ([5]). Let $A = M - N$ be an M-splitting of A . Then $\rho(M^{-1}N) < 1$ if and only if A is a nonsingular M-matrix.

Lemma 2.5 ([6]). Let A be a Z-matrix. Then A is a nonsingular M-matrix if and only if there is a positive vector x such that $Ax \geq 0$.

III. CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS AND COMPARISON THEOREMS

In this section, we will present the main theorems.

Theorem 3.1 Let $A = I - L - U$ be an M-matrix, where $-L$ and $-U$ are strictly lower and strictly upper triangular parts of A , respectively, $D_1 \geq 0$ and $0 \leq L_1 \leq L_\beta$. Then, the preconditioned mixed-type splitting iterative method is convergent.

Proof. Let

$$D_\beta = I - S_1, L_\beta = L - S_\beta + S_\beta L, U_\alpha = U + S_2,$$

where S_1, S_2 are the diagonal and upper triangular parts of $S_\beta U$. Then

$$M = D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta,$$

$$N = D_1 + L_1 + U_\beta.$$

Since A is an M-matrix and $0 \leq L_1 \leq L_\beta$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} M^{-1} &= (D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta)^{-1} \\ &= [(D_\beta + D_1) - (L_\beta - L_1)]^{-1} \geq 0, \\ A^{-1} &\geq 0, N = D_1 + L_1 + U_\beta \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

According to Lemma 2.1, Lemma 2.2 and Definition 2.3, we can get the conclusion that the preconditioned mixed-type splitting iterative method is convergent for M-matrix.

Corollary 3.1 The PSOR method is convergent if the coefficient matrix A is an M-matrix and $0 < r < 1$.

Corollary 3.2 The PAOR method is convergent if the coefficient matrix A is an M-matrix and $0 < r < w < 1$.

Theorem 3.2 Let A be a nonsingular Z-matrix, such that $D_1 \geq 0, 0 \leq L_1 \leq L_\beta, \beta \in [0, 1]$ and \tilde{T}, T are iterative matrices of (5) and (3), respectively. Then

(i) If $\rho(T) < 1$, then $\rho(\tilde{T}) < \rho(T) < 1$;

(ii) Assume that A is an irreducible matrix and $0 < a_{ii-1}a_{i-1i} < 1, i = 2, \dots, n$. Then

(1) If $\rho(T) > 1$, then $\rho(\tilde{T}) > \rho(T)$;

(2) If $\rho(T) = 1$, then $\rho(\tilde{T}) = \rho(T)$;

(3) If $\rho(T) < 1$, then $\rho(\tilde{T}) < \rho(T)$.

Proof. Let

$$M_\beta = D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta,$$

$$N_\beta = D_1 + L_1 + U_\beta,$$

$$M = I + D_1 + L_1 - L,$$

$$N = D_1 + L_1 + U,$$

$$E_\alpha = (I + S_\beta)(I + D_1 + L_1 - L),$$

$$F_\alpha = (I + S_\beta)(D_1 + L_1 + U),$$

then we get $A = M - N, A_\beta = M_\beta - N_\beta = E_\beta - F_\beta$.

(i) Since A is a nonsingular Z-matrix and $D_1 \geq 0, 0 \leq L_1 \leq L_\beta$, we can easily know that

$$M = I + D_1 + L_1 - L$$

is a nonsingular M-matrix and the splitting

$$A = M - N = (I + D_1 + L_1 - L) - (D_1 + L_1 + U)$$

is an M-splitting. Thus, $\rho(T) < 1$ and by Lemma 2.4, we know that A is a nonsingular M-matrix. Furthermore, we know that there exist a positive vector x such that $Ax \geq 0$ according to Lemma 2.5.

So

$$A_\beta x = (I + S_\beta)Ax \geq 0.$$

According to Lemma 2.5, A_β is also a nonsingular M-matrix.

Besides, since $L_\beta = D_\beta - I + L - S_\beta + S_\beta L + S_1$, we get $= (\lambda - 1)(D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta)^{-1}(S_\beta D_1 + S_\beta L_1 + S_1)x$.

$$\begin{aligned} E_\beta - M_\beta &= (I + S_\beta)(I + D_1 + L_1 - L) - (D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta) \\ &= (I + D_1 + L_1 - L) + S_\beta(I + D_1 + L_1 - L) \\ &\quad - (D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta) \\ &= I - L + S_\beta(I + D_1 + L_1 - L) - D_\beta + L_\beta \\ &= I - L + S_\beta(I + D_1 + L_1 - L) - D_\beta + D_\beta \\ &\quad - I + L - S_\beta + S_\beta L + S_1 \\ &= S_\beta(D_1 + L_1 + S_1) \geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

then

$$A_\beta^{-1}E_\beta - A_\beta^{-1}M_\beta = A_\beta^{-1}(E_\beta - M_\beta) \geq 0$$

and

$$A_\beta^{-1}E_\beta \geq A_\beta^{-1}M_\beta \geq 0.$$

Futhermor, we have

$$\rho(M_\beta^{-1}N_\beta) \leq \rho(E_\beta^{-1}F_\beta),$$

i.e.

$$\rho(\tilde{T}) \leq \rho(T) < 1.$$

(ii) Assume that $A = I - L - U$ is irreducible. Since $L + U$ is a nonnegative irreducible matrix, by the definitions of \tilde{T} and T , we can easily know that \tilde{T} and T are both nonnegative irreducible matrices.

If we let $\lambda = \rho(T)$, by Lemma 2.2, there exist a positive vector $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)^T$ such that $Tx = \lambda x$. That is equivalent to

$$(D_1 + L_1 + U)x = \lambda(I + D_1 + L_1 - L)x \quad (8)$$

and

$$(U - \lambda D + \lambda L)x = [(\lambda - 1)D_1 + (\lambda - 1)L_1]x. \quad (9)$$

If we let

$$S_\beta U = S_1 + S_2,$$

where S_1, S_2 are the diagonal and upper triangular parts of $S_\beta U$, then

$$\begin{aligned} A_\beta &= D_\beta - L_\beta - U_\beta \\ &= (I - S_1) - (L - S_\beta + S_\beta L) - (U + K_2) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$D_\beta = I - S_1, L_\beta = L - S_\beta + S_\beta L, U_\beta = U + S_2,$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{T}x - \lambda x &= (D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta)^{-1}(D_1 + L_1 + U_\beta)x - \lambda x \\ &= (D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta)^{-1}[(D_1 + L_1 + U_\beta) \\ &\quad - \lambda(D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta)]x \\ &= (D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta)^{-1}[(D_1 + L_1 + U + S_2) \\ &\quad - \lambda(I - S_1 + D_1 + L_1 - L + S_\beta - S_\beta L)]x \\ &= (D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta)^{-1} \{[(D_1 + L_1 + U) \\ &\quad - \lambda(I + D_1 + L_1 - L)]x + [S_2 - \lambda(-S_1 + S_\beta - S_\beta L)]x\} \\ &= (D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta)^{-1}[S_2 + \lambda(S_1 - S_\beta + S_\beta L)]x \\ &= (D_\beta + D_1 + L_1 - L_\beta)^{-1}(S_2 + \lambda S_1 - \lambda S_\beta + S_\beta L)x \end{aligned}$$

Since $D_1 + L_1 + I \geq 0$ and $S_\beta D_1 + S_\beta L_1 + S_1 \geq 0$, then
 (1) If $\lambda > 1$, then $\tilde{T}x - \lambda x \geq 0$, i.e. $\tilde{T}x \geq \lambda x$. By Lemma 2.3, we have $\rho(\tilde{T}) > \lambda = \rho(T)$.
 (2) If $\lambda = 1$, then $\tilde{T}x - \lambda x = 0$, i.e. $\tilde{T}x = \lambda x$. By Lemma 2.3, we have $\rho(\tilde{T}) = \lambda = \rho(T)$.
 (3) If $\lambda < 1$, then $\tilde{T}x - \lambda x \leq 0$, i.e. $\tilde{T}x \leq \lambda x$. By Lemma 2.3, we have $\rho(\tilde{T}) < \lambda = \rho(T)$.

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

For linear system $Ax = b$, where

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -0.1 & -0.1 & 0 & -0.2 & -0.4 \\ -0.3 & 1 & -0.2 & 0 & -0.3 & -0.2 \\ 0 & -0.2 & 1 & -0.5 & -0.1 & 0 \\ -0.1 & -0.3 & -0.1 & 1 & -0.2 & -0.1 \\ -0.2 & -0.3 & -0.2 & -0.1 & 1 & -0.1 \\ -0.3 & -0.1 & -0.1 & -0.2 & -0.1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

If we take $\beta_2 = \beta_3 = \dots = \beta_n \in [0, 1]$ and $D_1 = \frac{1}{2}I$, $L_1 = \frac{1}{5}L$, then by Theorem 3.1 and Theorem 3.2, we can obtain the following table:

TABLE I
Spectral Radius For Different Methods

β_i ($i = 2, \dots, n$)	$\rho(T)$	$\rho(\tilde{T})$
0	0.2930	0.2930
0.0500	0.2930	0.2915
0.1000	0.2930	0.2902
0.1500	0.2930	0.2890
0.2000	0.2930	0.2880
0.2500	0.2930	0.2871
0.3000	0.2930	0.2864
0.3500	0.2930	0.2858
0.4000	0.2930	0.2854
0.4500	0.2930	0.2852
0.5000	0.2930	0.2852
0.5500	0.2930	0.2853
0.6000	0.2930	0.2856
0.6500	0.2930	0.2861
0.7000	0.2930	0.2867
0.7500	0.2930	0.2874
0.8000	0.2930	0.2883
0.8500	0.2930	0.2893
0.9000	0.2930	0.2904
0.9500	0.2930	0.2915
1.0000	0.2930	0.2928

From Table I, we can conclude that the preconditioned mixed-type splitting iterative method is convergent and its convergence rate is faster than that of the mixed-type splitting iterative method.

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